

Effective Flexible e-learning Resource Based Cognitive Flexibility Hypertext Theory from learners viewpoint

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Description

The study aims to explore the impact of the e-learning process based cognitive flexibility hypertext theory on the achievement and attitudes of learners in Taibah University. Results show an effective online learning process based cognitive flexibility hypertext theory from learners viewpoints. Indeed, the average time to answer one achievement test is 7.21 minutes/10 minutes and the average of score of learners in the achievement test is 87%/100%. The attitudes of learners toward flexible e-learning process achieved through a questionnaire distributed to a sample of 143 learners show that the first rank is for the item "Solving learning difficulties of the e-learning resource" with an arithmetic mean equal to 1.51. The second rank is for the item "Sufficiency of time of the achievement test" with an arithmetic mean equal to 1.45.